

**A Study on the Perception of College Students'
towards Newspaper circulation in
Port Blair City**

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Abstract :

Print medium can be broadly classified into two parts namely periodical publications newspapers, magazines and the journals and publications of books and other printed materials. Newspaper shape public opinion. They criticize the work of the government. The government can know what the people feel about their work. The newspaper acts as a medium between people and government. They make people realize their duties and rights.

Introduction :

Newspapers play a vital role in one's daily life. The day starts with newspapers. They are the windows of the world. A newspaper means different things to different readers. Some readers are interested in political affairs. Some are interested in sports. Someone worried about share prices. Job seekers concentrate on advertisements. The important functions of mass media are to educate, to inform and to provide entertainment. These three functions are perfectly carried out by the print medium. Print medium can be broadly classified into two parts namely periodical publications newspapers, magazines and the journals and publications of books and

other printed materials. Newspaper shape public opinion. They criticize the work of the government. The government can know what the people feel about their work. The newspaper acts as a medium between people and government. They make people realize their duties and rights.

Utility of Newspaper when Compared with Internet :

From the table - 1, it is inferred that out of 120 respondents surveyed, 79.17% of the respondents state that the newspaper is more useful and the remaining 20.83% of the respondents state that the newspaper is less useful than Internet because many respondents do not have access to the internet.

Table - 1

Utility of Newspaper when Compared with Internet

S.No.	Usefulness of newspaper	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	More useful	95	79.17
2	Less useful	25	20.83
	Total	120	100.00

Source : *Primary data*

A Majority of 79.17% of the respondents state that the newspaper is more useful than Internet.

Opinion about Survival :

It is lucid from the table given below that, out of 120 respondents surveyed 74.16% of the respondents state that the newspaper will continue to survive and the remaining 25.84% of the respondents state that it is difficult for the newspapers to survive by competing with other communication technologies.

Table - 2
Opinion about Survival

S.No.	Opinion	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Continue to survive	89	74.16
2	Difficult to survive	31	25.84
	Total	120	100.00

Source : *Primary data*

A Majority of 74.16% of the respondents state that the newspaper will continue to survive, despite technological development.

Level of Satisfaction towards Newspapers contents :

From the below mentioned table it is depicts that the majority of the respondents are ranked employment news as first as compared to other contents of the newspaper.

Table - 3
Level of Satisfaction

News Contents	Very much satisfied		Satisfied		Not satisfied		Total	Rank
	Number of Respondents	Score	Number of Respondents	Score	Number of Respondents	Score		
Sports	53	159	48	96	19	19	274	V
Cinema	67	201	28	56	25	25	282	III
Religious	39	117	52	104	29	29	250	VII
Educational	62	189	34	68	24	24	281	IV
Employment	70	210	43	86	7	7	303	I
Current news	88	240	20	40	12	12	292	II
Political Affairs	52	156	33	66	35	35	257	VI

Source : *Primary data*

Suggestion :

- The newspapers are recommended to provide the readers with sufficient tips that would be useful at the time of tours and travels.
- Information regarding employment opportunities and competitive examinations can also be included under the regular day's schedule.
- It is found to be a better suggestion to reserve a few paragraphs of a page permanently for the empowerment of entrepreneurs. Here the matters that can be published are interviews with successful entrepreneurs, guidelines for starting various enterprises and so on.

Conclusion :

Newspapers now days have become one of the most important sources of information for a reader to know the things in depth. No doubt other media vehicles like television provide information but they may lack the inner course of action that is really wanted by the reader. The researcher tries to identify the main motivations that lead readers to read the newspapers and also the degree of perceived substitutability between digital and traditional newspapers.

References :

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